

Colleges of Education Lecturers' Awareness and Motivation to Utilise Online Resources for Instruction in Kwara State, Nigeria

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This study examined Colleges of Education Lecturers' awareness of and motivation to utilise online resources for instruction in Kwara State, Nigeria. The study adopted a survey research design. A total of 402 lecturers drawn from three colleges of education within Kwara State, Nigeria represent the sample for the study. Four research questions were raised and two research hypotheses were formulated and tested. The Research questions were answered using descriptive statistics mean and standard deviation while the hypotheses were tested using independent t-test, all the hypotheses were tested at 0.05 significant level, and the statistical tool used for analysis is Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS). The results revealed among others that lecturers are not aware of utilising online resources for instruction. Also, gender has no influence on lecturers' motivation in using online resources for instructional delivery. Based on the findings, it was concluded that colleges of education lecturers in Kwara State are relatively motivated to utilize online resources for instructional delivery. The implication of the study is that online resources could be easily integrated into education when adequate provisions were made to motivate lecturers' usage of the resources and proper awareness creation on available online resources for instruction. This further highlight critical gaps in awareness and suggest targeted interventions that could enhance the digital pedagogical landscape in developing economies, in the same vein, workable and friendly policy that will not be gender bias should be formulated to further strengthen lecturer' awareness and motivation to utilise online resources for instruction. It was recommended among others that; lecturers should develop more interest in the use of online resources; and find more ways they can be incorporated into teaching and learning.

Keywords:

Online resources, Utilise, Awareness, Motivation, Instruction,

Introduction

The use of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in the classroom to enhance student-centered learning process has become a key concern in educational research. Lecturers are now using software programs to help students improve their skills in all learning areas. The range of available technologies provides

lecturers at all levels with a plethora of options for differentiated instruction. The recognition of integrating ICT in teaching and learning requires access to a fuller range of resources. Using ICT for classroom instruction has a significant impact on students' learning and enables instruction to be delivered and received anytime and

anywhere, providing students with varied and convenient learning environments (Gomez, 2012).

Globally, there is a push towards integrating ICT in education, Kwara State's Colleges of Education have faced challenges in adopting these resources effectively, this is not unconnected to the fact that adequate provisions has not been made for effective integration resulting inadequate provision of ICT facilities, stable power supply among others, these and many other factors necessitated the need for this study.

However, with the advent of the Internet and ICT as a whole, educators have come to explore their various capabilities in instruction and learning, leading to the discovery of tools and resources that provide for better collaboration and interactivity between students and teachers. One of these is the use of Web 2.0- an online resource, which is an interactive technology in teaching that aims to enhance creativity, information sharing, and collaboration among users (Buan, 2008). In a Web 2.0 environment, users can work together and share responsibilities, collaborate with peers, experts, and community members to monitor and keep track of contributions, and use various kinds of technology to conduct research, communicate, and create knowledge. Online Resources include web pages and documents on the Internet that provide useful information. They are resources that are accessible via the Internet and the World Wide Web, and are typically data and educational in nature. It can also be seen as online technologies, which, according to Soetan and Coker (2018), are various internet resources, services, facilities, platforms, open educational resources, e-library resources, virtual resources, and social networks, among others, that are found on the global networks of computers. Traditionally, the

concept of awareness has been used in the research field of computer-supported collaborative work (CSCW) to re-establish the conditions of face-to-face situations in the online realm, with visual cues showing, for example, who is online or working on a document. Research on awareness support in the CSCW context has often been directly related to the direct improvement of cooperative practices and measurable improvements in task performance.

Literature Review

The need to enhance lecturers' subject matter and teaching techniques has increased in recent years. As a result, researchers have garnered significant and growing interest (Aagaard 2015; Figueiró & Raufflet 2015; Le Pelley et al 2016). Several studies, such as (Caro, Lenkeit, & Kyriakides, 2016; Du Boulay & Luckin, 2016; Hazari, North, & Moreland, 2019) suggest that differences in student learning can be largely attributed to teachers' awareness of specific instructional strategies. One of the main aims and objectives of UNESCO is to create awareness and motivation to utilize online resources for instruction, so that lecturers from different disciplines may know the importance of online resources in the teaching and learning process.

Awareness is the ability to perceive, feel, or be proactive about changes in the environment. Falode et al. (2018) defined awareness as the ability to perceive, feel, or be conscious of something. In other words, awareness is concerned with the development of well-informed interests in a particular situation (Gupta, 2020). Lecturers' awareness of online resources for instruction will help them locate the necessary free materials available for them to use. Though many lecturers in higher institutions of

learning may be aware of the existence of online resources for instruction, what is their perception about the usage of online resources for instruction?

Colleges of Education as one of the initial teacher training institutions certified by the National Commission for Colleges of Education (NCCE), the organization that controls the kind of students to be admitted and enforcement of minimum curriculum standard in teacher training, is at the forefront in the implementation and use of varied teaching strategies, the National Commission for Colleges of Education (NCCE) (2012).

To be prepared for the inclusion of technology in education, teachers need to be sensitized about the implications of its usage in the class and its impact on students' learning. Hope (1997) postulated that in adopting technology, the most confronting factors are teachers' reactions to the psychological effects of change and their learning to use microcomputer technology, especially for classroom purposes. Hence, the successful adoption of technology in the classroom is dependent on school administrators providing an individualized, differentiated process of training and implementation to educators (Gray, 2001). Readiness to use the Internet is fostered by the development of positive attitudes by university lecturers towards technology, acquisition of requisite skills, and external factors such as institutional readiness, which includes the school's provision of an ICT-enabled environment, as well as frequent motivation of staff to engage in technology for classroom instruction (Fisseha, 2011).

ICT's penetrating influence has affected the field of education (Abanikannda, 2011). ICT has greatly impacted teaching, learning, and research. Quality in traditional, as well as open and distance forms of

education. ICT is a vibrant tool for quality teaching and learning development; it speeds up the change in existing school practices and helps prepare students for the future. To be successful in implementing ICT policy, the importance of sectoral application to education and sustainable implementation must accord with the need for recognition (Yusuf, 2005).

Using ICT and its tools, online resources inclusive in all fields have witnessed great growth in the recent past, because technology incorporation into the classroom has become a component of instructional processes such that emerging technologies now challenge the old systems of instruction and how education is managed. ICT technology is an efficient tool for accelerating, enriching, and deepening skills and motivating and engaging students in learning; it also helps to link experiences in the school to practices in the workplace, thereby creating a viable economy soonest. Similarly, it contributes to basic changes in schools and provides a favorable policy for a good relationship between schools and the world (Willie, 2006). Other impacts of ICT on education as highlighted by Willie, (2006) include serving as a great potential to supplement traditional learning, provision of new opportunities to explore high level cognitive activities like creativity, autonomy, problem solving and team work, enhancing learning where students and teachers will be allowed to control, manipulate and contribute information to teaching and learning environments through the availability of interactive books, journals and the like via the Internet, improvement in the quality of teaching and learning related activities which is not limited only to Nigeria but also in sub-Saharan Africa via the adoption of new multimedia technologies and Internet,

facilitating interaction and collaboration among learners and teachers as well, both at local and global levels, giving opportunity to individuals who might wish to combine work and learning, hence, learning at his or her own pace, irrespective of location, enhancing lecturers' performance through course materials delivery and provides every time attention to students since they can now meet through email feedback facility or otherwise, thereby revolutionizing distance learning, thereby enhancing easy accessibility to education, giving room for attractive and interactive flexible user's interface; and providing accessibility, flexibility, and collaborative work to urban as well as rural dwellers through open and distance education. Motivation is an incentive that enables individuals to engage in a particular activity, usually until the accomplishment of certain set objectives. Motivation has been defined differently by different authors. Keller (2008) stated that motivation to learn is promoted when the knowledge to be learned is perceived to be meaningfully related to a learner's goals, especially within a conducive environment.

The influence of gender on the classroom utilization of technology also plays a major role in the selection, development, and achievement of instructional objectives. Van Braak (2001) proposed that female students have lower confidence or knowledge ability than male students when using computers. Onasanya, Shehu, Ogunlade, and Adefuye (2011) assert that given the low level of utilization of ICTs for instructional purposes in Nigeria, male teachers are more computer literate and utilize ICTs for instructional purposes than their female counterparts. However, current trends and technological advancements have seen an uptake of equal parity in the male and

female use of technological devices. A gradual change is felt, even across the education sector.

Comparatively, studies in similar contexts, such as (Sulaiman & Joshua, 2019; Ekhurutomwen & Akporhonor, 2020; Abubakar, Z. Katcha, M. A. & Dajal R.G., 2025;) have revealed various findings and suggested a global pattern in the challenges faced by lecturers in adopting online resources. Suleiman and Joshua (2019) conducted a study to investigate the awareness and utilization of the Internet resources and services for academic activities by the academic staff of tertiary institutions in Adamawa State, the study revealed that the academic staff of tertiary institutions in Adamawa State have a high level of awareness of usage of Internet resources and services. Also, a study on Awareness and Perception of Lecturers towards Using E-Learning Tools for Instructional Delivery in Universities was conducted by Ekhurutomwen and Akporhonor (2020). Findings from the study indicated that that lecturers are aware and have a good perception of the use of some E-learning tools for instructional delivery in universities. It equally revealed that the level of use of E-learning tools for instructional delivery in universities is very high for some E-learning tools such as smartphones, Google search, and personal computers. Others are Twitter, YouTube, CD ROMs, Google reader and digital television, while it is shallow for e-learning tools such as Audacity and Delicious while Abubakar, Katcha and Dajal (2025) studied Awareness and Utilization of Virtual Learning Resources among Science Lecturers in Colleges of Education in North Central Nigeria. It was revealed in their study that while science lecturers are fully aware of virtual learning resources, their utilization of

these resources remains limited.

In the same vein, researchers such as (Siti Nurul, Mohd Azran, & Sazilah, 2015; & Sunday et. al, 2022) carried out studies on lecturers' motivation to utilise online resources for instruction. Siti Nurul, Mohd Azran, and Sazilah, (2015), worked on Factors Affecting Lecturers Motivation in Using Online Teaching Tools. The result of their study revealed factors such as: knowledge, perception and skills affect lecturers' motivation in using online teaching tools. Sunday et. al (2022) carried out an empirical study on academic staff's motivation for online teaching in Nigerian universities: an empirical evidence from the university of Ibadan, the result of their findings revealed that most of the academic staff feel motivated to teach online.

However, erratic power supply, work overload, and limited knowledge of e-learning stand as major hindrances to online teaching adoption among academic staff.

Conceptual Frame Work

Frameworks have been proposed and developed for ICT and other related tools use

for teaching and learning. These are done to allow integration of IT and its tools into teaching and learning processes for improved instructional delivery by teachers and learning process by students. Hence, this study is premised on the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) (Davis, 1986) and Diffusion of Innovation Theory (DIT) (Rogers 2003).

Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) by Davis (1986) is an influential contribution to the enduring line of IT implementation and diffusion research. It posits that both perceived ease of use (PEOU) and perceived usefulness (PU) correlate with system use, a relationship that seems to explain fairly well why people accept or reject a technology, known as TAM. The model provides the basis by which traces can be made to how outer variables manipulate attitude, belief, and intention to use technology. Ultimately, a belief about the system, PU and PEOU in TAM, directly affect attitudes toward use. The model is illustrated in figure 1.

Figure 1: Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) by (Davis, 1986)

Diffusion of Innovation Theory (DIT) by Rogers (2003) is a broad social psychological theory that describes the patterns of adoption, explains the mechanism and assist in predicting whether and how a new invention will be successful. Diffusion of Innovation seeks to explain how innovations are taken up in a population and describes the ways by which new invention will be adopted and when it will be adopted. An invention is a

behaviour or idea of object that is perceived as latest by its audience. Rogers (2003) however defined the adopter categories to mean the classifications of participants of a social system based on innovativeness. The classifications are: innovators, early adopters, early majority, late majority and laggards. The categorization is represented in figure 2.

Figure 2: Adopter Categorization on the basis of Innovativeness (Sahin, 2006).

Rogers (2003) observed that DIT gives three valuable in-depth explanations into the process of social change: what qualities make an innovation spread (perceived characteristics of innovations), the importance of peer conversations and peer networks (social system variables) and understanding the needs of different user segment (receiver variables).

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study were to:

1. Find out lecturers’ awareness on utilising online resources for instruction
2. Examine the level of lecturers’ motivation to utilise online resources for instruction

3. Determine the influence of gender on lecturers’ awareness to utilise online resources for instruction.
4. Determine the influence of gender on lecturers’ motivation to utilise online resources for instruction.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide study.

1. what is the level of lecturers’ awareness on utilising online resources for instruction?
2. how motivated are lecturers to utilise online resources for instruction?

3. what is the influence of gender on lecturers' awareness to utilise online resources for instruction?
4. what is the influence of gender on lecturers' motivation to utilise online resources for instruction?

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. there is no significant difference on lecturers' awareness to utilise online resources for instruction based on gender.
2. there is no significant difference on lecturers' motivation level to utilise online resources for instruction based on gender.

Methodology

This is a descriptive study of the survey type. Descriptive research reports situations in which they are, and as this is what is expected of this study, the method is thought to be appropriate. This research employed a Google form researcher-designed questionnaire to elicit information from respondents on lecturers' awareness of online resources for instruction, as well as their level of motivation to utilize online resources for instruction. Gender was also taken into consideration. The target population for the study was all lecturers in the Colleges of Education, Kwara State, Nigeria. Out of 402 lecturers in the three state-owned Colleges of Education in the state, only 116 adequately participated and responded to the online questionnaire. From this sample, 24 were female and the remaining 92 were male.

The validity of the instrument was ensured by five experts from School of Science and Technology Education, Federal University of Technology, Minna, Niger State and three experts from the department of Computer Science, Kwara State College of Education,

Oro. The reviewers helped to review the questionnaire to check the clarity of language and ensured it is relevant to the study. Their suggestions and corrections were noted and effected on the final draft of the instrument administered. The reliability of the research instrument was determined by administering twenty copies of the questionnaire to randomly selected lecturers from Niger State College of Education, Minna, Nigeria. After the administration and retrieval of the completed instrument, their responses to the items were subjected to statistical analysis using Cronbach alpha reliability statistics to check for the instrument's internal consistency. The Cronbach's alpha value obtained was 0.76 at 0.05 level of significance. This indicates that the instrument is reliable.

The instrument consists of three sections. Section A examined the respondents' bio data, section B has to do with the respondents' awareness of online resources for instruction, and section C has to do with the respondents' level of motivation to utilize online resources for instruction. The study used a four-point Likert scale (Strongly Agree, Agree, Disagree and Strongly Disagree).

The research questions were answered using descriptive statistics such as mean and standard deviation, while the hypothesis was tested using independent t-test statistics. This is because the variable in the study, that is, the gender of the respondents, was an independent variable occurring at two levels: male and female lecturers. The lecturers' responses to the questionnaire items, which were the dependent variable, were treated as score data. The questionnaire items were then subjected to inter-rater agreement to determine the extent of agreement of the respondents who participated in the study to the awareness and motivational level to utilize online resources for instruction.

Results

Research Question 1: What is the level of lecturers' awareness of the utilization of online resources for instruction?

Table 1:
Descriptive Analysis of Lecturers' Awareness to Utilise Online Resources for Instruction

S/N	Items	Mean	Std. Deviation
1	I am aware that Online Resources for Instruction (ORI) exist	2.45	0.895
2	Online resources for instruction are readily available for use, reuse, and research	1.92	1.014
3	Online resources provide quality free materials for teaching	2.03	0.995
4	Online resources can be used effectively for teaching	2.14	0.986
5	Online resources complement normal class teaching	2.14	1.003
6	Online resources can be freely shared among colleagues	2.20	1.065
7	Online resources provide feedback for teaching and learning activities	1.97	1.029
8	Online resources foster collaboration and innovation among lecturers	1.99	1.034
9	Online resources encourage the globalization of curriculum	2.00	1.013
10	Adoption of online resources advance openness and sharing of intellectual property	2.02	1.013

Table 1 show that the lecturers have negative awareness impression about online resources for instruction because majority of them disagreed with the statements on their awareness about online resources for

instruction. The mean values greater than or equals to 2.5 means agreement with the statement and the mean values less than 2.5 means disagreement. Hence, all the statements are lesser than 2.5

Research Question 2: How motivated are lecturers to utilise online resources for instruction?

Table 2: Descriptive Analysis of lecturers' motivation level to utilise online resources for instruction

S/N	Items	Mean	Std. Deviation
11	Utilizing online resources for instruction	2.29	1.427
12	Using online resources to enhances my teaching effectiveness	2.27	1.447
13	Using Online resources to make my teaching more efficient	2.37	1.466

14	Investing time in learning how to use online resources	2.34	1.415
15	My institution supports the use of online resources for instruction	2.24	1.362
16	Having access to the necessary technology to use online resources effectively	2.23	1.347
17	Receiving adequate training on how to use online resources for instruction	2.66	.895
18	Feeling confident in my ability to use online resources for instruction	2.78	.931
19	To believe that online resources can improve student learning outcomes.	2.53	1.489
20	Peer support and collaboration in using online resources for instruction	2.27	1.447

Table 2 shows that some of the lecturers are unmotivated about online resources for instruction because some of them who disagreed with the statements on their level of motivation about online resources for instruction has the mean value gotten from the analysis to be less than 2.5, while few of the lecturers are highly motivated about online resources for instruction because few

of them agreed with the statements on their level of motivation about online resources for instruction and their mean value gotten from the analysis was greater than 2.5.

Hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no significant difference in lecturers’ awareness of the use of online resources for instruction based on gender.

Table 3: T-test of Male and Female Colleges of Education Lecturers Awareness to Utilize Online resources for Instruction

Group	N	Mean	SD	Df	t-value	Sig. (2-tailed)	Decision
Male	92	20.8696	6.62200	114	.050	.960	Not Accepted
Female	24	20.7917	7.30681				

Table 3 shows that $t(114) = 0.050, p=.960$. This means that the t-value of 0.050, which results in a significant value of 0.960, was greater than 0.05. Hence, the null hypothesis was not rejected. This implies that there is no difference between male and female

lecturers’ awareness of utilizing online resources for instruction.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference in lecturers’ motivation level to utilize online resources for instruction based on gender.

Table 3: T-test of Male and Female Colleges of Education Lecturers' Motivation level to Utilize Online resources for Instruction

Group	N	Mean	SD	Df	t-value	Sig. (2-tailed)	Decision
Male	92	23.8804	8.06545	114	.281	.779	Not Accepted
Female	24	24.4167	9.23564				

Table 4 shows that $t(114) = 0.281$, $p = .779$. This means that the t-value of 0.281, which results in a significance value of 0.779, was greater than 0.05. Hence, the null

Discussion, Conclusion and Recommendations

Research question 1 was used to determine the level of lecturers' awareness of utilizing online resources for instruction. This was done to determine the lecturers' prior knowledge of the availability or existence of online resources for instruction. The results of the study indicated that a larger percentage of the respondents (lecturers) were unaware of the online resources for instruction. This result is not in tandem with findings from the studies of Sulaiman & Joshua, 2019; Ekhurutomwen & Akporhonor, 2020; Abubakar, Z. Katcha, M. A. & Dajal R.G., 2025; whose results indicated high levels of awareness of Internet resources and service, lecturers having good awareness of E-learning tools and science lecturers are fully aware of virtual learning resources but with limited utilization respectively. Research question 2 addressed the motivation of lecturers to utilize online resources for instruction. This is to identify how effectively the lecturers were motivated to make the best use of the available online resources for instruction in terms of provision of necessary facilities such as stable power supply or alternative provision, provision of Internet facilities, and making available for use. It was

hypothesis was not rejected. This implies that there is no difference between male and female lecturers' motivation levels to utilize online resources for instruction.

discovered from the study that there was no adequate provision of facilities and infrastructure to motivate the lecturers to utilize online resources for instruction. This result is not in tandem with findings from the studies of Sunday et. al (2022) whose findings revealed that most of the academic staff feel motivated to teach online.

The influence of gender on lecturers' awareness of utilizing online resources for instruction was confirmed by Hypothesis 1. The results of the study indicated no gender influence on lecturers' awareness to utilize online resources for instruction in state-owned colleges of education in the Kwara state. Similarly, Hypothesis 2 was used to determine the influence of gender on lecturers' motivation of utilizing online resources for instruction. It was revealed that gender plays no significant role in lecturers' motivation level to utilize online resources for instruction.

However, based on the results presented in this study, it was concluded that the majority of the colleges of education lecturers in Kwara State were unaware of online resources for instruction, while they were relatively motivated to utilize online resources for instructional delivery. Similarly, gender had no influence on

lecturers' awareness and motivation to utilize online resources for instruction.

Hence, to enhance lecturers' awareness of online resources for instruction in Kwara State, a detailed action plan including quarterly workshops/trainings and an online repository of resources tailored to the needs of Kwara State lecturers could be established by the government. The implication of the result from the present study applying Rogers' Diffusion of Innovation Theory and Technology Acceptance Model is that there is a low awareness levels among lecturers, this is as an indication of the early stages of technology adoption in Kwara State's educational institutions. Though, online resources could be integrated into education with adequate provision of facilities and proper awareness of their availability for instructional delivery.

Based on the findings and conclusions of this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Adequate awareness should be created for lecturers about online resource availability for instruction so that they develop more interest in the use of these resources for instruction.
2. Lecturers are encouraged to find more ways to incorporate online resources into teaching and instructional delivery.
3. The government and management of state-owned colleges of education should put in place policies for increased lecturers' level of motivation to use online resources for instruction as well as to sustain the policies.

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